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Evaluation & Impact Assessment
GENDER APPRAISAL

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>ENGAGING & INCENTIVISING INTERROGATING CREATING ADDRESSING APPLYING EVALUATION & IMPACT ASSESSMENT</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>At the beginning of a project/initiative and during implementation, as required.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Whole multi-actor group, small to large. Particularly useful for large consortia where there are different levels of knowledge about gender.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>Some technical skills required, involving the use of a simple survey tool.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>Approx. 2 hours in total. Survey preparation takes about 1 hour. Survey completion takes 10-15 minutes for participants. Results can be summarised in less than an hour. Gender Appraisal can be repeated as necessary, with the option to compare results throughout the lifetime of the project/initiative.</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>Requires basic materials, little or no cost. Free survey tools are available online.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tool # 3, 19.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source: Teagasc.

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- Raise awareness of gender within the project or initiative.
- Evaluate if gender balance has been achieved at the project and leadership level within the project or initiative.
- Assess gender balance at different points during the project or initiative.
- Invite project partners to reflect on how they will incorporate gender into their project tasks.
- Provide information for project coordinators to help identify if any further actions are required.

Background and Logic

Projects/initiatives that are gender-balanced at the project and leadership level, and include considerations of gender in their tasks are more successful and innovative. This means it is important to ensure gender balance at the project level and within the project leadership team while also including consideration of gender in tasks, particularly at the beginning of a project or initiative. Projects with large or small consortia may have different levels of knowledge and awareness of gender, which must be monitored and led.

This tool enables recording of gender types participating at project and leadership level at the start, and periodically throughout the project. The tool also encourages reflection on the relevance of gender to project/initiative tasks. The tool raises awareness of gender within the consortium and highlights if there are gaps in knowledge, which could require further action.

Materials

- Survey tool (paper or online)

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

Step 1: Preparation

- Adapt the Gender Appraisal survey tool template (below) to the needs of the project/initiative. Note: Question 2. is optional, may be relevant for formal projects with specified work packages.
- Prepare a brief introduction to the survey tool to explain why it is being used at this time in the project/initiative (if distributing the tool online, this can be a brief email).
- Obtain names and email addresses of all project participants per institution/partner and issue the email invitation to complete the survey individually, with assurance (using Research Ethics or GDPR compliance documents, where relevant) that all data will be treated anonymously and analysis presented anonymously.

Gender Appraisal Tool Template	Women	Men	Non-binary	Prefer not to say
1. Number of people in the work package with a leadership role:				
2. Number of people with a ask leadership role:				
3. Number of people without a leadership role:				
4. Any comments? For example, if a male worked on the project at the start and was replaced by a female employee, please elaborate and implications/changes here. Any other comments are welcome.				
5. Please explain if and how gender is relevant to the work (insert examples) you undertake for, as you perceive it?				

Step 2: Distribute the Survey to All Project Participants

- Ensure enough time is allowed to complete the survey. The survey must be involved. Email reminders are useful for participants completing the online format.

Step 3: Presenting Survey Data

- A summary table can be used to illustrate survey results, showing the numbers of people in each category and responses to the final question.
- Repeated summary tables are issued after each periodic issuing of the survey.

Step 4: Further Actions

- Participants take other actions to raise awareness of gender in projects. Examples:
 - » A project team member adding an email banner including gender-awareness quotes to their electronic signature.
 - » A dedicated slot at team meetings to discuss issues of gender. Recent discussion items have been discussions of gendered implications of COVID-19.

